

coefficient in the hybrids. It should be possible to increase GSR and BY simultaneously in hybrids, but not in parents.

The multiple regression equation for GY heterosis was $GY = 4.609 + 0.100 DH + 1.039 CN + 0.068 FSN + 0.429 GW + 0.312 BY + 27.286 GSR$. This model was effective in predicting GY heterosis, accounting for 88% of the total variation (Table 2). Except for DH, the effect of the

regression was highly significant. Biological yield was the most important contributing character in the formation of GY heterosis.

Heterosis of GY depends on heterosis of BY, FSN, CN, PH, PL, FSP, GW, and GSR. It would be helpful in hybrid rice breeding to take into account the heterotic relationships among some metrical characters. □

Table 1. Correlation coefficients for heterosis of F₁ and parents among 11 characters.^a

Trait		DH	CN	PL	PH	TSN	FSN	FSP	GW	BY	GSR	GY
DH	P	1										
	F ₁											
CN	P	-0.2	1									
	F ₁											
PL	P	.78**	-0.10	1								
	F ₁											
PH	P	.81**	.02	.92**	1							
	F ₁											
TSN	P	.49*	-.37	.48*	.52*	1						
	F ₁											
FSN	P	.76**	-.38	.76**	.69**	.68**	1					
	F ₁											
FSP	P	.44*	-.14	.39	.23	-.20	.57*	1				
	F ₁											
GW	P	.18	-.34	.25	.31	-.16	.12	.26	1			
	F ₁											
BY	P	.85**	.18	.81**	.84**	.32	.68**	.48*	.37	1		
	F ₁											
GSR	P	-.61**	-.23	-.53*	-.58**	-.35	-.36	-.08	-.02	-.56*	1	
	F ₁											
GY	P	.81**	.19	.77**	.80**	.28	.71**	.56*	.36	.98**	-.48	1
	F ₁											

^a Correlation coefficients for parents (P) and F₁ below the diagonal, those for heterosis above the diagonal. **, * = significant at 5 and 1% levels, respectively.

Table 2. Statistical test for the model of grain yield heterosis.^a

SV	DF	SS	@	MS	F	R ²
DH	1	5.503	6	5.503	2.66	
CN	1	21.734	3	21.734	10.49**	
FSN	1	18.942	4	18.942	9.14**	
GW	1	16.097	5	16.097	7.77**	
BY	1	47.109	1	47.109	22.73**	
GSR	1	37.017	2	37.017	17.86**	
Multiple regression	6	976.366		162.728	78.51**	0.8787
Error	65	134.722		2.073		
Total	71	1111.090				

^a @ = magnitude order of SS, ** = significant at the 1% level.

Restorers and maintainers for two cytoplasmic male sterile lines

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In a hybrid rice breeding program based on a cytoplasmic male sterility and fertility restoration system, identification of effective maintainers and restorers is of great importance. We crossed 10 short-, medium-, and long-duration rice cultivars with cytoplasmic male sterile lines Zhen Shan 97 A and V20 A in 1988 wet season

at Ranbir Singh Pura, Jammu, and Kashmir. The F₁ hybrids were evaluated for spikelet fertility during the 1989 wet season.

Varieties showing more than 80% spikelet fertility were classified as restorers; those with 30-79%, 1-29%, and less than 1% spikelet fertility were rated as partial restorers, partial maintainers, and effective maintainers, respectively.

All test cultivars except Dular, IET10770, and N22 were identified as restorers (see table). N22 partially restored the fertility of both cytoplasmic sterile lines. IET10770 and Dular were classified as effective maintainers. □

Restorers and maintainers for 2 cytoplasmic male sterile lines identified at RARS, R.S. Pura, India, 1989 wet season.^a

Variety	Spikelet fertility	
	Zhen Shan 97 A	V20 A
IR35454-18-1-2-2	R	R
IR25912-30-2-3-2	R	R
IR29692-99-2	R	R
IR9761-19-1-R	R	R
B4227 E-KN-10	R	R
IET10321	R	R
IET10770	M	M
IET1410	R	R
Dular	M	M
N22	PR	PR

^a R = restorer (80% spikelet fertility), PR = partial restorer (30-79% spikelet fertility), PM = partial maintainer (1-29% spikelet fertility), M = maintainer (less than 1% spikelet fertility).

Heterosis in physiological attributes of rice hybrids

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Heterosis in yield characters of F₁ rice hybrids from cytoplasmic genetic male sterile (CMS) lines has been well recognized. Information on the heterosis of physiological characters, however, is meager.

We studied standard heterosis over check Jaya of seven F₁ hybrids (six from CMS line IR54752 A and one from Madhu A) during 1989 wet season (Jul-Oct). The hybrids and Jaya were transplanted (25 d after seeding) at 20 × 15-cm spacing, one seedling/hill, in a